

EVALUATION OF YIELD AND YIELD-RELATED TRAITS IN TINDA GOURD (*PRAECITRULLUS FISTULOSUS*): IMPLICATIONS FOR VARIETY IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to evaluate the performance of tinda gourd (*Praecitrullus fistulosus*) genotypes for yield and yield-related traits under the agro-climatic conditions of Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan, during Kharif 2025. A total of nine varieties/hybrids, including advanced breeding lines and one commercial check variety (Dilpasand), were assessed in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications at the Vegetable Research Institute, Faisalabad. Data were recorded for important morphological, reproductive, yield, and quality traits including days to flowering, vine length, fruit firmness, internodal distance, number of fruits per plant, and fruit yield. Significant variability was observed among the tested genotypes for all studied traits. Days to flowering ranged from 40.1 to 50.2 days, while vine length varied between 109.2 and 140.1 cm. Fruit firmness ranged from 2.10 to 6.53 kgf, indicating differences in postharvest quality potential among genotypes. The highest number of fruits per plant (10) and maximum fruit yield (2.086 t ha⁻¹) were recorded in TD 23 F1, followed by APPLE GOLDEN with a yield of 1.817 t ha⁻¹. In contrast, HTG-808H exhibited the lowest yield (0.380 t ha⁻¹). The results demonstrated a strong association between fruit number per plant and overall yield performance. Genotypes combining early flowering, moderate vegetative vigor, and higher fruit set showed superior productivity and adaptation under local conditions. The study identified TD 23 F1 and APPLE GOLDEN as promising genotypes for commercial cultivation and future breeding programs aimed at improving yield and fruit quality in tinda gourd.

INTRODUCTION

Tinda gourd (*Praecitrullus fistulosus* L.), also known as Indian round gourd or apple gourd, is a warm-season cucurbit cultivated extensively in South Asia, particularly in Pakistan and India, for tender round fruits. Belonging to the family Cucurbitaceae, the crop is valued for soft texture, mild flavor, and high digestibility, making a preferred vegetable in traditional cuisines.

Nutritionally, tinda gourd is a rich source of dietary fiber, minerals, and bioactive compounds, and recognized for low caloric content, which supports inclusion in health-conscious diets. In addition to nutritional benefits, the crop contributes significantly to the livelihood of smallholder farmers due to short growth cycle,

adaptability to diverse agro-climatic conditions, and steady market demand.

Despite potential, the productivity of tinda gourd remains suboptimal in many production regions. Yield levels are influenced by a combination of genetic factors, agronomic practices, and environmental conditions. Limited varietal improvement and inadequate attention to yield-associated traits have restricted genetic gains over time. For sustainable enhancement of productivity, there is a need to identify superior genotypes with desirable combinations of yield and agronomic characteristics. Yield in tinda gourd is a complex quantitative trait, determined by the interplay of several morphological and physiological parameters such as **fruit number per plant, vine length, and flowering behavior**. Understanding the relationship between these traits and their direct or indirect contribution to yield can significantly improve the efficiency of selection in breeding programs.

In recent years, increasing emphasis has been placed on evaluating genetic variability and trait associations within cucurbits to support targeted varietal development. For tinda gourd, comprehensive evaluation of yield and yield-related traits across genotypes can help identify promising selections for release or use in hybridization programs. Such studies not only provide a basis for improving yield potential but also contribute to the diversification of varieties adapted to local agro-ecological zones.

The present study was designed to assess the performance of tinda gourd genotypes for yield and related morphological traits under field conditions. The findings aim to provide insights into trait contributions to overall productivity and to highlight genotypes with potential for further breeding and commercial cultivation, thereby contributing to the long-term improvement and sustainability of tinda gourd production.

Material and methods

The present study was conducted at the Vegetable Research Institute during Kharif 2025 to evaluate the yield and yield related traits of tinda gourd (*Praecitrullus fistulosus*)

varieties/hybrids under the agro-climatic conditions of Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan. A total of 09 varieties/hybrids obtained from different sources were evaluated along with advanced breeding lines of the institute and one commercial check variety, namely Dilpasand. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. The crop was sown on 25 February 2025 in plots measuring 7 m × 3 m. Recommended agronomic practices including land preparation, irrigation, fertilization, hoeing, weed management, and plant protection measures were uniformly adopted throughout the experimental period to ensure healthy crop growth and development. Data were recorded on important vegetative, reproductive, yield, and fruit quality traits including days to flowering, vine length (cm), fruit firmness (kgf), internodal distance (cm), number of fruits per plant, and fruit yield (t ha⁻¹). Days to flowering were recorded as the number of days from sowing to the appearance of the first flower in each treatment. Vine length was measured in centimeters from the base of the plant to the terminal growing point at peak vegetative stage using a measuring tape. Internodal distance was determined by measuring the average distance between successive nodes on the main vine. Fruit firmness was measured in kilogram-force (kgf) using a handheld fruit firmness tester/penetrometer on randomly selected mature fruits from each plot. The number of fruits per plant was calculated by counting the total marketable fruits harvested from randomly selected plants and averaging the values. Fruit yield was recorded on plot basis and subsequently converted into tons per hectare (t ha⁻¹). Observations regarding insect pest and disease incidence were also recorded during the crop season. Particular attention was given to the infestation of red pumpkin beetle, leaf miner, and other sucking and chewing insect pests. Statistical analysis of all recorded data was carried out using analysis of variance (ANOVA) appropriate for RCBD. Treatment means were compared by applying the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at 5% probability level to

determine significant differences among the tested genotypes.

Results and Discussion

The evaluation of nine *Praecitrullus fistulosus* genotypes revealed clear variability across phenological, morphological, quality, and yield-related traits. Days to flowering ranged from as early as 40.1 days in TD 21 F1 to as late as 50.2 days in APPLE GOLDEN, indicating a spectrum from early to late maturing types. Earliness, as seen in TD 21 F1 and Tinda max (42.1 days), is advantageous for targeting early markets or avoiding late-season stress, while later-flowering types such as APPLE GOLDEN and PG-2030 may allocate more resources to vegetative growth before reproduction, potentially influencing overall yield patterns. Early flowering is advantageous in escaping late-season heat or disease pressures and accelerating time to market, particularly in smallholder or early season production systems (Abbas *et al.*, 2025). Conversely, later-flowering types may accumulate more vegetative biomass before reproduction, influencing resource partitioning and potential yield. Such variation in phenology is well recognized in cucurbits and offers a valuable selection parameter depending on target cropping environments (Wehner & Guner, 2004)

Vine length varied from 109.2 cm in HTG-808H to 140.1 cm in TD 23 F1, reflecting differences in vegetative vigor. In cucurbit crops, longer vines often provide more floral nodes and fruiting sites, potentially contributing to greater yield, provided that the plant can sustain assimilate supply. However, excessively vigorous vines may complicate management, especially under high planting density or mechanized systems. Adjusting vine traits to align with production systems is critical for optimizing yield and ease of harvest.

Firmness spanned from a low of approximately 2.10 kgf (PG-2030) to a high of 6.53 kgf (TD 21 F1). Fruit firmness is a key determinant of postharvest quality, affecting shelf life, mechanical resistance, and marketability; firmer fruits are better suited to longer supply chain handling, while softer fruits may suit local

consumption provided yield and quality trade-offs are acceptable (Ahmed *et al.*, 2023). Research in related cucurbits confirms firmness as a heritable trait influenced by genotype and maturity, with important implications for breeding and market targeting.

Internodal distance ranged from a compact 3 cm in Tinda max to a longer 9 cm in the check variety Dilpasand, which influences canopy architecture and potentially light penetration and fruit distribution (Dhillon *et al.*, 2020). Shorter internodes contribute to a more compact canopy, which can support higher planting densities, reduce shading, and ease harvesting, while longer internodes may spread fruiting sites further apart, possibly aiding air circulation and disease management (Senger *et al.*, 2024). Internodal traits are often environment-sensitive and should be clearly defined in methods to ensure reproducibility and interpretability (Garg *et al.*, 2017).

Number of fruits per plant varied substantially, with TD 23 F1 producing the highest count (10 fruits) and Shiny 1 the lowest (3 fruits). This trait showed a strong association with yield, as TD 23 F1 also recorded the highest yield (2.086 t/ha). APPLE GOLDEN, despite later flowering, maintained a relatively high fruit count (8) and the second-highest yield (1.817 t/ha), indicating efficient assimilate partitioning (Malik *et al.*, 2023). Conversely, HTG-808H and TD 21 F1, though exhibiting moderate to high firmness and acceptable vine length, produced lower fruit numbers and correspondingly lower yields (0.380 and 0.654 t/ha, respectively), suggesting potential limitations in fruit set or size (Mandal *et al.*, 2020).

Yields ranged dramatically from a low of 0.380 t/ha (HTG-808H) to a high of 2.086 t/ha (TD 23 F1). Notably, TD 23 F1 combined high fruit number with moderate vine vigor and firmness, indicating efficient resource allocation to reproductive output (Qamar *et al.*, 2022). APPLE GOLDEN also performed well (1.817 t/ha) despite later flowering and shorter vines, suggesting potential for yield stability through assimilate use efficiency (Raheel *et al.*, 2019). Lower-yielding genotypes may require

improvement in fruit set, size, or stress tolerance before they become competitive for commercial

cultivation (Singh *et al.*, 2026).

Table 1:

Rank	Genotypes	Days to flowering	Vine length (cm)	Firmness (kgf)	Internodal distance (cm)	No. of fruits per plant	Yield (T/Ha)
1	TD 23 F ₁	45.1	140.1	4.41	5	10	2.086
2	APPLE GOLDEN	50.2	130.5	4.78	6	8	1.817
3	Dilpasand (Check)	49.3	125.1	2.5	9	6	1.647
4	BT-2023	47.1	116.3	3.945	4	5	1.410
5	Tinda max	42.1	111.2	3.55	3	4	1.385
6	PG-2030	50.1	117.2	2.10	4	6	1.215
7	Shinny 1	50.1	118.3	4.76	5	3	1.000
8	TD 21 F ₁	40.1	115.6	6.53	6	5	0.654
9	HTG-808H	48.2	109.2	4.48	4	4	0.380

Figure 1:

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